

SOME THEORY ABOUT SUB-GROUPS OF TRANSLATION

Saidova Hurriyat Zafar kizi

(Student of SamSIFL)

Annotation: *This article is written about translation of scientific and technical texts must meet the following requirements: adequacy, equivalence, information content, accuracy and logical presentation. Moreover, in addition to knowledge of translation techniques, the translator needs to have knowledge of the field of knowledge and terminology of the specific technical field to which the text belongs. This is the main difficulty of such a translation, because the translator must be a highly qualified versatile specialist who not only knows the language perfectly, understands linguistic aspects, but also owns technical disciplines, which allows him to deeply understand the essence of the translated text.*

Key words: *translation, text, technical translation, selective translation, oral annotation.*

Technical translation is used for the exchange of specific scientific and technical information between people who speak different languages, in other words, it is the translation of technical literature, such as scientific and technical articles, instructions, business contracts, etc.

A well-executed technical translation means that the style of the original text is maintained, the translated text, in turn, reflects the main features of the scientific and technical style: brevity and clarity of presentation, adherence to technical terminology, consistency in following information, unambiguous interpretation of facts.

As for the process of working on a translation, first a specialist translator, who also knows a technical specialty, works on the translation. Then, an editor works on the text, proofreading the final translation, and already at the last stage of the work, a

native translator can connect, who carries out a deep adaptation of the text for subsequent use by foreign readers.

It should be noted that the translation of scientific and technical texts has certain features, the main of which is the ambiguity of English words. Here the translator's skill lies in the ability to correctly select the meaning that most fully reflects the meaning of the term in each specific case.

Another significant problem is the presence of abbreviations and abbreviations in the texts, which can cause difficulties in interpretation even for technical specialists. Also, a lot of difficulties are caused by new words that have not yet officially taken root. In such cases, the translator has to look for the most appropriate translation of the word, which would be fully consistent with the original. In addition, the discrepancy between the requirements for abbreviations, GOSTs adopted in different countries, which can differ significantly from each other, also makes translation difficult. [2]

Translation in the field of information technology is becoming more and more in demand in the market of translation services every day. Translation of instructions and manuals for the maintenance of various devices and programs, technical descriptions for equipment and much more - all this refers to IT translation. Today it is already impossible to imagine the development of enterprises, individual sectors of the economy without the use of information technology. Of course, the vast majority of IT products are created in English, as the international language of communication, so the task of a translator is to adapt these products into other languages. At the same time, the breadth of use and the competitiveness of the product in a particular country depend on the correctness of the translation.

The problem of performing a high-quality translation on IT topics is that professional linguists, having only a humanitarian education, usually have a poor orientation in the subject area of translation. Therefore, constant active work in a specialty related to the field of IT technologies is extremely important for them.

It should be noted that translations in the field of information technology have certain features:

- in addition to the abundance of specialized terminology, the use of slang vocabulary is very characteristic, which can significantly complicate the understanding of the text and the translation process as a whole;

- binding to the English language (the main developers in the field of IT technologies are mainly the United States of America);

- active borrowing and widespread use of words (especially computer terminology) by people using information technology products. This is where the problem of “translating – not translating?” arises;

- rapid obsolescence of terminology (sometimes in 2-3 years);

- use of different terminology by competing corporations in software development;

All of the above suggests that higher requirements are placed on IT translators. In addition, such a translator must have an interest in innovation and be constantly ready to exchange experiences and improve their skills. [5]

Thus, the translator must remember and take into account all the nuances of translation in a specific technical area and be sure to constantly update his knowledge in a specific area of technical knowledge in order for the translations to be adequate, equivalent and meet quality indicators.

Consultative translation - a type of interpretation, including oral annotation, oral abstracting, selective translation from sight and interpretation of headings, performed by a consultant-translator referent-translator who can use the customer's knowledge as the main source of special information.

Thus, there are 5 types of technical translation in total: full written translation, abstract translation, abstract translation, express information type translation and consultative translation, each of which has a set of application rules and a sequence of execution.

The task of an interpreter-consultant is to help specialists who have little or no command of a foreign language to understand what is being said. It helps specialists to select the right material and make a decision on the issue of further processing of the material. The consultant interpreter makes an annotation or abstract on the material he has, for which, in any case, a careful study of the context is necessary.

LITERATURE

1. Бархударов Л. С. Язык и перевод (Вопросы общей и частной теории перевода). / Л. С. Бархударов - М.: «Международ. отношения», 1975. - 240 С.
2. Усачев В.А. Актуальные проблемы перевода научно-технических текстов в английском языке – Донецк: ВІСНИК ДонНУЕТ. - № 2 (58). - 2013. – С. 177-188
3. Даминов Н. К. СИНХРОН ТАРЖИМАНИНГ АСОСИЙ ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ //PEDAGOGIK ISLOHOTLAR VA ULARNING YECHIMLARI. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 66-69.
4. Daminov, Navruz. "Using some strategies in simultaneous interpreting process." E3S Web of Conferences. Vol. 381. EDP Sciences.
5. Daminov N. K. SIMULTANEOUS TRANSLATION INTERPRETING AS A MODERN TYPE OF TRANSLATION //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 2. – С. 77-81.
6. Kudratovich D. N. SOME VIEWS ABOUT TRANSLATION STRATEGY //International Congress on Models and methods in Modern Investigations. – 2023. – С. 15-17.
7. Ziyotova Ra'no Utkir kizi. (2023). FEATURES AND TECHNIQUES OF WRITTEN TRANSLATION . ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 19(3), 32–35. Retrieved from <http://www.newjournal.org/index.php/01/article/view/5067>
8. Saidova Hurriyat Zafar kizi. (2023). FEATURES OF SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL STYLE . ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 19(3), 40–44. Retrieved from <http://www.newjournal.org/index.php/01/article/view/5069>
9. Khasanxonova Durdonakhon Juraxon kizi (2023) DEFINITION AND METHODS OF TRANSLATION PROCESS. 176–179. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7802951>
10. Nurmamatovna N. S. GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ORAL TRANSLATION. – 2023.